

Research Article

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Author for correspondence:

Vu Thi Mai Huong

✉ huongvtm@hnue.edu.vn

✉ Hanoi National University of Education, Hanoi, Vietnam

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Cluster-Informed Policy Design for School Administrators in Vietnam: A Data-Driven Perspective on Digital Readiness

Nguyen Thi Minh Nguyen^{id}, Vu Thi Mai Huong^{id}, Bui Quang Vinh^{id}, Pham Ngoc Long^{id}

Abstract

Background/purpose. Digital transformation in education is a key factor in improving the quality of teaching and school management. However, readiness for digital transformation is not solely a matter for teachers—it is also a critical concern for school managers. This study employs cluster analysis to assess the digital transformation readiness of school managers.

Materials/methods. Based on responses from 264 participants who are managers of general education schools in Vietnam, the study applies unsupervised machine learning for clustering.

Results. The results indicate that managers in more favorable areas are generally more prepared for digital transformation than those in less advantaged regions. Awareness of digital transformation, confidence in using technology, and perceived usefulness of technology are significant determinants of readiness.

Conclusion. By uncovering readiness profiles, the findings offer direct implications for differentiated policy design, targeted investment, and leadership training. The study proposes a cluster-informed approach to digital education reform, supporting evidence-based decision-making by policymakers and educational leaders.

1. Introduction

Digital transformation in education has become a central focus of global education policies. The integration of technology not only aims to enhance the quality of teaching but also contributes to improving the efficiency of school management and developing the professional competencies of both teachers and administrators (Metcalf & LaFrance, 2013; Hamzah et al., 2021; Abdullah & Kadir, 2023). In the context of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and the rapid advancement of digital technologies—especially in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic—the need to assess the readiness of educational institutions for digital transformation has become increasingly urgent (Gordashnikova et al., 2021; Kirinić et al., 2023; Samosa et al., 2023).

Digital transformation in education extends beyond the mere use of technological devices; it encompasses comprehensive changes in management processes, decision-making approaches, and the development of digital leadership capabilities (Makri & Vlachopoulos, 2019; Kin & Kareem, 2019; Koniari & Raftoulis, 2023). In this context, school management teams—particularly principals—play a pivotal role in leading and organizing the implementation of digital transformation initiatives within their schools (Oberer & Erkollar, 2018; Zeng et al., 2024; Nailufar et al., 2023; Marfan, J., & Pascual, J., 2018; Razak et al., 2023; Ridho & Wiyono, 2024). However, without effective digital leadership, efforts to implement educational technologies can face unintended setbacks. Asante and Novak (2024) showed that when digital leaders fail to manage the interplay between motivating and constraining factors in technology adoption, the integration of digital resources may backfire, leading to low engagement and increased resistance among educators.

However, digital transformation is a complex and challenging process. Numerous studies have indicated that its success largely depends on the readiness of individuals and organizations to embrace change (Weiner et al., 2008; Kurmanov, N., Bakirbekova, A., & Adilbekuly, M., 2024). While much of the existing research focuses on the readiness of teachers and students, in-depth investigations into the digital transformation readiness of school administrators remain relatively scarce (Samosa et al., 2023; Moradi & Keshmiri, 2021). This gap became particularly evident during the COVID-19 pandemic, when many school systems struggled to shift to online teaching. According to König, Jäger-Biela, and Glutsch (2020), early-career teachers in Germany encountered significant challenges due to the limited digital competence support provided by school leaders. Their findings underscore the pressing need to assess and enhance digital readiness at the management level.

Developing digital leadership capacity is a prerequisite for school administrators to formulate effective transformation strategies and support teachers in integrating technology into their teaching practices (Abdullah & Kadir, 2023; Makri & Vlachopoulos, 2019; Abdullah, N. S., & Kadir, S. A., 2023). The success of digital transformation relies not only on technological tools but also on the transformation of organizational culture, which demands initiative, adaptability, and innovative capacity from leaders (Hoa, 2022; Oberer & Erkollar, 2018). In line with this, Masoumi and Noroozi (2023) emphasized that institutional support from school leaders plays a critical role in developing early-career teachers' digital competence. Their review found that strong leadership practices—including mentorship and collaborative digital environments—greatly facilitate the integration of technology at the classroom level.

Furthermore, research has shown that educational administrators often encounter significant challenges in implementing digital transformation, such as limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient personal technological competence (Kirinić et al., 2023). According to Kurmanov, N., Bakirbekova, A., & Adilbekuly, M. (2024), the absence of digital leadership skills can create obstacles in technology implementation and may lead to resistance from both teachers and students.

Top management support is also crucial in fostering an environment conducive to successful digital transformation (Zeng et al., 2024; Nababan et al., 2021). When principals and school leadership teams demonstrate strong commitment and collaboration, teachers are more likely to actively embrace and utilize technology in teaching and learning activities.

Therefore, this study is significant in examining the level of digital transformation readiness among school management teams, particularly in the context of Vietnam, where digital transformation is being vigorously promoted by the Government and the education sector. The findings of this research can provide valuable input for policy formulation, training program development, and the professional development of school leaders in alignment with the requirements of comprehensive digital transformation in education (Luić et al., 2020; Weiner, 2009; Wijayati et al., 2023).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Digital Transformation in Education

Digital transformation in education refers to the integration of digital technologies into school management and teaching practices to enhance educational effectiveness, foster innovation in pedagogical methods, and support flexible, personalized learning experiences for students (Gordashnikova, Fedorchuk, & Kuznetsov, 2021). The implementation of digital transformation requires more than just technological infrastructure—it also demands a comprehensive framework for assessing the digital competencies of both teachers and administrators, such as the DigCompEdu framework (Redecker, 2017; Ghomi & Redecker, 2019; Carretero, Vuorikari, & Punie, 2017).

Readiness for digital transformation is influenced by various factors, including technology infrastructure, supportive government policies, and, most importantly, the digital capabilities of school staff (Latifah, Budiyanto, & Saputro, 2022; Wijayati et al., 2023). According to Tan (2022), principals' digital leadership plays a pivotal role in establishing effective digital learning environments—from strategic planning and professional development for teachers to overseeing and enhancing digital teaching and learning processes. Recent studies continue to emphasize digital leadership's critical role in ensuring digital transformation initiatives' success (Abdullah & Kadir, 2023; Koniari & Raftoulis, 2023; Berkovich & Hassan, 2022; Okunlola, 2024). Abdullah and Kadir (2023) assert that principals' digital leadership has a positive impact on teachers' technological competencies, especially in the post-pandemic educational landscape. Likewise, Koniari and Raftoulis (2023) contend that school managers' digital skills not only influence technology integration but also contribute significantly to fostering a culture of innovation within educational institutions. Asante and Novak (2024) add that digital leaders must effectively manage both motivating and hindering factors in digital resource use to avoid implementation failures.

In the context of Vietnam, Hoa (2022) emphasizes that digital transformation is not merely the application of technology but a comprehensive restructuring of educational management activities. This transformation demands that educational leaders possess strategic thinking, a willingness to embrace change, and a commitment to continuous learning to meet the demands of the Fourth Industrial Revolution and the broader global integration trend (An & Thuy, 2023).

2.2. Digital Transformation Context in Vietnam's Education

In Vietnam, digital transformation is directed toward the dual goal of developing a digital government, economy, and society while simultaneously fostering Vietnamese digital technology enterprises with the capacity to compete globally. Education and training are among the eight prioritized sectors in the national digital transformation program through 2025, with a vision extending to 2030 (Minister, 2020).

Digital transformation has become—and will continue to be—a mandatory requirement for educational institutions to ensure progress in planning, maintain training quality, and align all management and instructional activities with the goal of sustainable development. This contributes to the training of high-quality human resources, thereby supporting national economic development (Minister, 2021).

In the field of general education, digital transformation has received special attention from the Government and the Ministry of Education and Training, as evidenced by the issuance of numerous policy directives, comprehensive roadmaps, and detailed implementation guidelines. General education institutions are prioritized in applying digital transformation policies aligned with the goals of educational innovation, focusing on promoting learner-centered approaches that foster the development of students' qualities and competencies.

A significant aspect of this transformation is the rapid development of online educational environments and technology platforms for teaching and learning. These platforms have enabled schools to maintain flexible and effective instructional activities, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic and in the post-pandemic period (Minister, 2022).

Compared to other educational levels, general education has seen more clearly defined policies for developing digital competencies among teachers. These include large-scale online training programs, detailed guidance on technology integration in teaching, and professional standards that incorporate digital transformation and IT application competencies (MOET, 2021; MOET, 2023).

Notably, the Ministry of Education and Training has proactively issued a set of indicators to assess the level of digital transformation in general education institutions. These indicators focus on three main pillars: management activities, teaching and learning, and staff development (MOET, 2022). The digital competency requirements for general education teachers go beyond using digital materials or attending online training. They include the ability to design digital lessons, manage classes via technological platforms, and effectively utilize data for student assessment and management.

This comprehensive approach reflects the strategic priority placed on general education in Vietnam's digital transformation roadmap, supported by coordinated investment and clear directives from both central and local authorities.

2.3. The Role of School Leaders in Digital Transformation

In the context of technology-driven educational innovation, school leaders—particularly principals—are increasingly recognized as critical factors in shaping and implementing digital transformation strategies (Makri & Vlachopoulos, 2019; Hamzah, Nasir, & Wahab, 2021). Digital leadership competencies encompass not only the technical ability to use digital tools but also the capacity to inspire others, foster innovation, and support the professional digital development of teachers (Samosa, Blanquisco, & De Leon, 2023).

Research indicates that principals with strong digital leadership skills are more likely to cultivate positive learning environments, encourage pedagogical innovation, and promote the effective integration of digital technologies in teaching (Kirinić, Hrustek, & Mekovec, 2023; Koniari & Raftoulis, 2023). According to Marfan and Pascual (2018), school leaders play a pivotal role in developing a clear vision for digital transformation, building a supportive organizational culture, and ensuring coordinated efforts among staff members. Moreover, empirical studies such as those by König, Jäger-Biela, and Glutsch (2020) emphasize the lack of digital readiness among school leaders during the COVID-19 crisis, highlighting the need for systemic leadership development.

Moreover, effective digital leadership contributes to sustainable improvements in school operations, driving innovation not only in instructional practices but also in management processes

(Raftoulis, 2021; Lazaridou & Polymeropoulou, 2024; Cheng & Wang, 2023; Khofi & Santoso, 2024; Nurjani et al., 2025). These findings reaffirm the indispensable role of school leaders in advancing comprehensive and sustainable digital transformation in education.

2.4. Readiness for Digital Transformation in Education

Readiness for digital transformation in education is a critical determinant of the successful integration of technology into teaching and school management. According to Weiner, Amick, and Lee (2008), readiness can be assessed through three key components: technological competence, the perceived value of technology, and the ability to sustain its application in practice. These components significantly influence the implementation of digital transformation strategies within educational settings.

The DigCompEdu framework (Redecker, 2017) has been widely adopted to evaluate the digital competence of both teachers and school leaders, thereby serving as an indicator of an institution's overall readiness for technology integration (Carretero, Vuorikari, & Punie, 2017). Weiner (2009) further emphasized that organizational culture, leadership commitment, and the innovation capacity of the staff are essential for ensuring sustainable digital transformation.

Beyond individual competencies and institutional culture, readiness is also shaped by external factors such as government policies, technological infrastructure, and financial resources (Latifah, Budiyo, & Saputro, 2022; Wijayati et al., 2023). Tan (2022) and Gordashnikova et al. (2021) highlight that the principals' ability to coordinate resources, provide professional development, and foster a supportive environment plays a crucial role in the success of digital initiatives.

More recently, Zeng, Alias, and Mansor (2024) emphasized the mediating role of digital leadership in linking policy frameworks, technological capacity, and pedagogical practices in schools. Their findings, along with those of De La Rosa (2019) and Kuzmina-Merlino (2024), reinforce the importance of leadership in aligning digital transformation efforts with broader institutional goals. Their findings, along with those of De La Rosa (2019), Kuzmina-Merlino (2024), and Masoumi and Noroozi (2023), reinforce the importance of leadership in aligning digital transformation efforts with broader institutional goals.

This study contributes to the existing literature on digital transformation in education by introducing a novel perspective on assessing school administrators' readiness. Drawing from Weiner's (2009) theory of organizational readiness for change and its operationalizations (Shea et al., 2014; An & Thuy, 2023), the study proposes a four-dimensional framework that reflects psychological and cognitive aspects of digital change: commitment, belief in effectiveness, perceived value, and information evaluation.

Unlike prior research that often emphasizes teacher digital competencies (Redecker, 2017; Fernández-Batanero et al., 2023), this study shifts the analytical lens to school leadership. By doing so, it aligns with emerging perspectives that highlight the principal's digital leadership as a key enabler of successful transformation (Abdullah & Kadir, 2023; Koniari & Raftoulis, 2023; König, Jäger-Biela, & Glutsch, 2020; Masoumi & Noroozi, 2023)

Additionally, the integration of cluster-based statistical techniques with educational measurement advances the methodological discourse in educational management research (MacQueen, 1967; Rousseeuw, 1987). This approach allows for the identification of distinct readiness profiles and facilitates the development of differentiated intervention strategies—an analytical strength that remains underutilized in current literature.

Finally, the study responds to calls for more context-sensitive models in digital transformation, particularly in developing countries (Gordashnikova et al., 2021; Zeng et al., 2024), by providing

empirical evidence from Vietnam's general education system. The results are potentially transferable to other education systems facing similar infrastructure, policy, and leadership challenges.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative approach with a correlational survey design. The research aims to identify clusters of school administrators based on their readiness for digital transformation and to examine the relationships between demographic variables and readiness levels. A non-experimental design was used, focusing on natural variations in attitudes and perceptions rather than manipulation of variables.

3.2. Instruments

A cluster analysis approach was utilized to address the research questions. The factors associated with readiness for digital transformation (DT) and the corresponding DT readiness assessment scale were developed based on the organizational readiness for change framework proposed by Weiner (2009). This scale was further refined by Shea et al. (2014) and subsequently adapted by An and Thuy (2023). According to this framework, the dependent variable—DT readiness—consists of four latent constructs representing essential aspects of digital transformation: (A) Commitment to change driven by digital transformation, (B) Beliefs regarding the effectiveness of such change, (C) Perceived value of the change, and (D) Evaluation of information related to digital transformation. These constructs were operationalized through a set of 30 survey items. The survey instrument was divided into two parts: the first collected demographic data, including name, gender (male/female), and geographic location; the second assessed participants' perceptions of school principals' readiness for digital transformation. To ensure the instrument's validity, an expert in educational science and assessment collaborated in the survey development process.

3.3. Research samples

The study conducted a survey using questionnaires designed and distributed via Google Forms between June and August 2024, targeting school principals and administrators across various regions in Vietnam. According to (Decision No. 861/QĐ-TTg), ethnic minority and mountainous areas in Vietnam are classified into three zones based on socio-economic development levels: Zone I (1,673 communes with relatively favorable conditions), Zone II (210 communes with moderate difficulties), and Zone III (1,551 communes with extreme difficulties). In this study, communes in Zone III are designated as disadvantaged areas for the purpose of analyzing disparities in digital transformation readiness across regions. This classification aligns with the official national framework issued by the Vietnamese Government. This online approach ensured accessibility, efficiency, and broad geographic reach—an approach widely adopted in educational research due to its cost-effectiveness (Stern, Bilgen, & Dillman, 2014). A total of 264 complete and valid responses were collected and included in the analysis.

Content validity was established through expert review by a panel of three specialists in educational leadership and digital transformation. The measurement tool shows high reliability, as shown by the Cronbach's Alpha coefficient as follows:

- Commitment to change: $\alpha = 0.89$
- Belief in effectiveness: $\alpha = 0.87$
- Perceived value: $\alpha = 0.91$
- Information assessment: $\alpha = 0.86$
- Overall scale: $\alpha = 0.90$

These values exceed the 0.70 threshold commonly recommended for social science instruments, indicating satisfactory reliability (Taber, 2018).

Reliability and construct validity were further supported through data preprocessing and analysis using the KNIME Analytics Platform—a robust open-source platform that supports reproducible workflows and visual data manipulation (Berthold et al., 2009). KNIME was integrated with Python scripting nodes to facilitate machine learning model application (e.g., PCA and k-means), statistical evaluations, and standardized data transformation.

The initial raw dataset consists of 264 tuples (records) and 35 data fields (variables), representing responses collected from school managers. These data fields include demographic information, technology usage patterns, perceptions of digital transformation, and self-assessed digital competencies. Figure 1 shows the process of building machine learning and clustering models.

Figure 1. Experimental Procedure for Clustering Analysis

This procedure outlines the steps taken in the data preprocessing, clustering analysis, and evaluation phases, including data cleaning, normalization, application of the k-means algorithm, selection of optimal cluster numbers using the Silhouette index, and visualization of results using multidimensional scaling (MDS).

3.4. Data Cleaning

In the original dataset, several responses contained missing values in specific attributes. Figure 1 shows cases of missing data during testing.

Table 1. Missing data in specific attributes of the original dataset

No.	Record ID	Missing Attributes
1	11	D2 – Resources for digital transformation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have experience implementing digital transformation in schools. • I have enough time to implement digital transformation activities in the school.
2	25	D1 – Understanding digital transformation tasks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know what resources are needed to implement digital transformation in the school.
3	35	D1 – Understanding digital transformation tasks: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know how much time is needed for digital transformation. • I know how much funding is required. • I know what resources are needed.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know what actions need to be taken. • I know what my role is in the digital transformation process.
4	75	<p>D2 – Resources for digital transformation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have enough time to implement digital transformation activities in the school.
5	132	<p>D2 – Resources for digital transformation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I have enough time to implement digital transformation activities in the school.
6	139	<p>D1 – Understanding digital transformation tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know what resources are needed to implement digital transformation in the school.
7	179	<p>D1 – Understanding digital transformation tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know what actions need to be taken.
8	235	<p>D1 – Understanding digital transformation tasks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I know what resources are needed to implement digital transformation in the school.

To ensure the dataset is complete and to avoid errors during model training and clustering, the responses from records 11, 25, 35, 75, 132, 139, 179, and 235 were removed. After this data-cleaning process, the dataset was reduced to 256 complete records.

3.5. Data Normalization

Several categorical fields in the dataset are normalized into numerical values to ensure consistency and compatibility for clustering analysis. Table 2 shows the normalization values in this study.

Table 2. Normalization of categorical variables

Data Field	Original Value	Normalized Value
Work Location	Disadvantaged, rural, mountainous areas	1
	Urban areas (cities, towns, townships)	5
Gender	Male	1
	Female	0
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	1
	5 – 10 years	5
	10 – 15 years	10
	15 – 20 years	15
	More than 20 years	20

All other variables that were already in numerical format were kept unchanged for further processing.

3.6. Data Transformation

In this experiment, the Standardization method was used for data transformation. Standardization is a technique that transforms data so that the mean (μ) of the values becomes 0 and the standard deviation (σ) becomes 1. This method is robust against outliers and preserves the statistical characteristics of the data. The transformation is performed using the following formula 1:

$$x_{standardization} = \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- x is the initial data value,
- μ is the mean value based on the data set,
- σ is the standard deviation.

After applying standardization, all features in the dataset are rescaled to have a mean of zero and unit variance, which is particularly important for clustering algorithms like k-means, which are sensitive to differences in scale. The dataset after applying the standardization method is shown in Figure 2.

#	RowID	Địa bàn c... Number (dou...)	Giới tính Number (dou...)	Thâm niên... Number (dou...)	A Sự cam... Number (dou...)	A Sự cam... Number (dou...)	A Sự cam... Number (dou...)	B Niêm ti... Number (dou...)	B Niêm ti... Number (dou...)	B Niêm... Numbe
1	Row0	0.859	-1.391	-3.313	-1.186	-1.123	-1.174	-1.032	-1.063	-0.884
2	Row1	0.859	-1.391	-3.313	-0.197	-1.123	-0.192	-0.02	0.034	0.126
3	Row2	0.859	0.716	-1.474	0.792	0.86	0.791	-0.02	-1.063	-0.884
4	Row3	0.859	-1.391	-3.313	0.792	0.86	0.791	0.992	1.132	1.136
5	Row4	0.859	-1.391	-1.474	0.792	0.86	0.791	0.992	1.132	1.136
6	Row5	0.859	0.716	-3.313	0.792	0.86	0.791	0.992	1.132	1.136
7	Row6	0.859	-1.391	-3.313	-1.186	-1.123	-1.174	-1.032	-1.063	-0.884
8	Row7	0.859	-1.391	-2.496	0.792	0.86	0.791	-0.02	0.034	0.126
9	Row8	0.859	-1.391	-3.313	-2.174	-2.114	-2.157	-1.032	-1.063	-0.884
10	Row9	0.859	-1.391	-2.496	-0.197	-0.132	-0.192	-0.02	0.034	0.126
11	Row10	0.859	-1.391	-2.496	-0.197	0.86	0.791	-0.02	0.034	0.126

Figure 2. Standardized dataset after applying the standardization method

3.7. Dimensionality Reduction using PCA

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a widely used technique for reducing the dimensionality of datasets in machine learning and deep learning applications. It transforms high-dimensional data into a lower-dimensional form while preserving the most significant information, typically by maximizing the variance captured in the principal components.

The PCA process includes the following steps:

Data Standardization ensures that all features are on the same scale, which is crucial since PCA is sensitive to differences in measurement units.

- Covariance Matrix Computation: The covariance matrix reflects the relationships and dependencies between variables in the dataset.
- Computation of Eigenvalues and Eigenvectors: In PCA, eigenvectors determine the orientation of the principal components, while the corresponding eigenvalues quantify the variance explained by each of those components.

- Selection of k Principal Components: After calculating the eigenvectors and eigenvalues, a subset of k principal components is selected such that the chosen components retain the most significant variance in the data—typically based on a cumulative variance threshold.

By reducing the number of features, PCA helps to decrease memory usage and computation time during model training. Additionally, PCA can reduce noise in the dataset, retaining only the most informative features. This process enables the model to concentrate on the most significant patterns in the data, which can enhance its predictive performance and ability to generalize to new, unseen data. Machine learning algorithms such as K-Means, SVM, or KNN often perform better on dimensionally-reduced data, as distance calculations between data points become more reliable and less influenced by irrelevant features.

In this study, the research team selected k = 2 principal components, reducing the original 35 dimensions to 2, to facilitate both model training and data visualization using 2D plots.

Figure 3. PCA configuration interface with selected variables for dimensionality reduction to 2 components

► 1: Filtered table Flow Variables

Rows: 256 | Columns: 2 Table Statistics

#	RowID	PCA dimension 0 <i>Number (double)</i>	PCA dimension 1 <i>Number (double)</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	Row0	-5.356
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	Row1	0.004
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	Row2	-1.567
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	Row3	3.967
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	Row4	4.181
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	Row5	5.919
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	Row6	-5.549
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	Row7	0.16
<input type="checkbox"/>	9	Row8	-4.15
<input type="checkbox"/>	10	Row9	0.177
<input type="checkbox"/>	11	Row10	-0.586

Figure 4. The resulting dataset with two principal components after PCA transformation

The top panel in Figure 3 shows the PCA configuration dialog, where the dataset is reduced to 2 dimensions using the selected variables. The bottom panel, illustrated in Figure 4, displays the resulting table with 256 rows and two newly computed features: PCA dimension 0 and PCA dimension 1, representing the transformed principal components used for clustering and visualization.

3.8. Cluster Analysis Techniques Used

This study utilized the k-means clustering algorithm to categorize school administrators into distinct subgroups based on their digital transformation readiness. As an unsupervised learning method, k-means effectively partitions data into non-overlapping clusters sharing similar characteristics (MacQueen). K-means was selected due to its effectiveness in handling large datasets, its simplicity in implementation, and its ability to produce easily interpretable cluster centers based on Euclidean distances. Furthermore, its compatibility with PCA-transformed data and integration within the KNIME and Python environments made it well-suited for this study's data pipeline.

The algorithm was applied to the PCA-reduced dataset (2 dimensions \times 264 observations). Several values for k (number of clusters) were tested, specifically k = 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6, to explore different segmentation possibilities. To assess how well the data points fit within their assigned clusters and how distinct each cluster is from the others, the Silhouette coefficient was applied as a measure of clustering validity (Rousseeuw, 1987). The Silhouette coefficient quantifies the appropriateness of a data point's assignment to a particular cluster by comparing its similarity within the assigned cluster to its dissimilarity with the nearest alternative cluster. The metric is defined by the following formula (2).

$$S(i) = \frac{b(i) - a(i)}{\max(a(i), b(i))} \quad (2)$$

Where:

- a(i) represents the mean distance between the i-th point and all other points within the same cluster, reflecting intra-cluster cohesion.
- b(i) denotes the average distance between the i-th point and all points in the closest neighboring cluster, indicating inter-cluster separation.

The Silhouette index ranges in value from -1 to 1, where values closer to 1 indicate better-defined and well-separated clusters. A Silhouette score near 1 indicates that data points are well matched to their own cluster and distinctly separated from neighboring clusters, reflecting high clustering quality. Scores around 0 suggest overlapping clusters where data points lie close to the decision boundary between clusters, indicating ambiguous cluster assignments. Values approaching -1 imply that data points may have been assigned to incorrect clusters, signifying poor clustering performance and possible misclassification. Formular (3) presents the formula used to compute the Silhouette index.

$$S = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n S(i) \quad (3)$$

Where:

- n represents the total number of data points,
- S(i) denotes the Silhouette coefficient for the ii-th data point.

This aggregate metric offers an evaluation of the clustering appropriateness and is commonly utilized to select the optimal number of clusters (k) in the k-means algorithm.

3.9. Data Analysis

Cluster analysis is a fundamental statistical technique in machine learning that aims to group objects based on shared features or patterns. In educational research, clustering is frequently employed to uncover groups of students who exhibit similar learning behaviors or attributes. Clustering methods are typically categorized into two primary types: hierarchical clustering and non-hierarchical (partitioning) clustering.

Hierarchical clustering constructs a binary tree-like structure, known as a dendrogram, which connects data points based on their similarity. This approach enables the exploration of clustering relationships at multiple levels of granularity. On the other hand, non-hierarchical clustering methods, such as partitioning algorithms, segment the dataset into a specified number of clusters without forming any hierarchical linkage among them.

The k-means algorithm, originally proposed by MacQueen (1967), begins by randomly initializing qq centroids within the dataset. Each data point is then assigned to the nearest centroid based on a distance metric, typically Euclidean distance. After the assignment, centroids are recalculated as the mean position of all points within each cluster. This process repeats iteratively until the centroids converge—that is, when their positions remain unchanged across successive iterations (Faizan et al., 2020).

One of the key limitations of the k-means algorithm lies in its sensitivity to both the initial selection of centroids and the predefined number of clusters. To address this issue, the algorithm is typically executed multiple times with varied initializations to improve robustness. The Silhouette Index (Rousseeuw, 1987) is commonly employed to assess the effectiveness of clustering outcomes, as it provides insight into both the cohesion within clusters and the separation between them. A higher silhouette value for a data point suggests a better fit within its assigned cluster relative to other clusters.

To aid in the interpretation of clustering results, multidimensional scaling (MDS) is frequently employed. This technique projects high-dimensional data onto a two-dimensional plane while preserving the relative distances between data points. As a result, it enables a visual representation of cluster structure and distribution across the dataset (see e.g., Borg & Groenen, 1997).).

4. Results

4.1. Clustering Results

Table 3 summarizes the outcomes of the k-means clustering analysis performed with varying numbers of clusters, ranging from $k=2$ to $k=6$.

Table 3. Silhouette Scores for Different Numbers of Clusters

Clusters (k)	Silhouette Scores	Figures
2	c_0: 0.482 c_1: 0.67 overall: 0.642	

3

c_0: 0.449
 c_1: 0.436
 c_2: 0.6
 overall: 0.487

4

c_0: 0.215
 c_1: 0.501
 c_2: 0.347
 c_3: 0.616
 overall: 0.376

5

c_0: 0.398
 c_1: 0.43
 c_2: 0.494
 c_3: 0.39
 c_4: 0.538
 overall: 0.453

6

c_0: 0.409
 c_1: 0.277
 c_2: 0.437
 c_3: 0.482
 c_4: 0.266
 c_5: 0.629
 overall: 0.422

The notation c_i (where $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$) refers to the clusters generated by the k-means algorithm. For example, c_0 corresponds to cluster₀.

As observed in Table 3, the K-Means model with 2 clusters achieves the highest Silhouette score (0.642), indicating clear and effective separation between the two identified clusters. Although increasing the number of clusters from 3 to 6 produces visually distinguishable groups (as seen in the scatter plots), it does not lead to significant improvement in cluster separation based on the Silhouette index. Consequently, this study selects $k=2$ as the optimal number of clusters, as it outperforms cluster configurations with 3, 4, 5, and 6 groups in terms of clustering quality.

4.2. Inter-cluster relationships

The results presented in Table 4 reveal noticeable differences in attribute values between the two clusters. The work location variable suggests that Cluster 0 tends to represent rural areas (mean value: 3.10), while Cluster 1 is more associated with urban areas (mean value: 3.33), although the distinction is not particularly sharp. In terms of gender, the proportion of male participants is slightly higher in Cluster 0 (68.4%) than in Cluster 1 (65.5%), but this difference does not appear to significantly impact the clustering results. As for years of experience, Cluster 1 has a slightly higher average (17.26 years compared to 16.92 years in Cluster 0), suggesting that school administrators in urban areas may have slightly longer tenures than those in rural areas.

Table 3. Comparison of Key Variables between Cluster 0 and Cluster 1

Data Field	Cluster 0 (Mean)	Cluster 1 (Mean)	General Evaluation
Work location	3,10526316	3,33027523	Cluster 1 tends to represent urban areas, while Cluster 0 leans toward rural areas (although the difference is not large).
Gender	0,68421053	0,6559633	Gender distribution does not differ significantly between the clusters; however, Cluster 0 has a higher proportion of male respondents. Male-to-female ratio in Cluster 0: 68.4% : 31.6% Male-to-female ratio in Cluster 1: 65.5% : 34.5%
Years of experience	16,9210526	17,2614679	The years of experience are nearly equivalent between clusters, with Cluster 1 being slightly higher.
A. Commitment to change through digital transformation	2,39473684	4,51376147	Cluster 1 shows significantly higher commitment. Individuals in this cluster demonstrate stronger motivation and readiness for digital transformation.
B. Belief in the effectiveness of digital transformation	2,23684211	4,33027523	Cluster 1 exhibits stronger belief in the effectiveness of digital transformation, indicating they perceive real benefits and feasibility.

C. Perceived value of digital transformation	2,39473684	4,35321101	Members of Cluster 1 demonstrate a higher level of awareness regarding the significance and benefits of digital transformation within their schools and professional activities.
D. Evaluation of information about digital transformation	2,28947368	3,97706422	Cluster 1 evaluates information more positively than Cluster 0, although the gap is smaller compared to other criteria. This may suggest that access to information is not the most decisive factor in the cluster differences.

The variable "Work Location" was initially coded numerically based on self-reported area types. While Cluster 1 showed a slightly higher average value (3.33) than Cluster 0 (3.10), this should not be oversimplified as a strict rural–urban divide. Urban areas, though often assumed to be more advantaged, also vary significantly—peri-urban and outer districts may face infrastructure limitations similar to rural zones (Trinh & Trinh, 2023).

The differences between the two clusters become more apparent in attributes related to digital transformation. Cluster 1 demonstrates significantly higher levels of commitment (4.51) and belief in the effectiveness of digital transformation (4.33) compared to Cluster 0 (2.39 and 2.23, respectively). Similarly, the perceived value of digital transformation is considerably higher in Cluster 1 (4.35) than in Cluster 0 (2.39), indicating that individuals in Cluster 1 not only show greater motivation but also a stronger belief in the practical benefits of digital transformation.

Conversely, Cluster 0 displays lower scores across these critical attributes. In terms of evaluation of digital transformation information, Cluster 1 again scores higher (3.97) than Cluster 0 (2.28), although the difference is less pronounced than in other attributes. This may suggest that information access and clarity, while important, are not the most decisive factors in the clustering outcome.

Based on these results, it can be inferred that Cluster 0 necessitates focused interventions aimed at strengthening the implementation and impact of digital transformation in educational institutions. Specifically, commitment to digital transformation is a key factor, as Cluster 0 shows a notably low score (2.39) compared to Cluster 1 (4.51). This implies the need for programs or strategies aimed at increasing motivation and readiness among schools in Cluster 0. Likewise, belief in the effectiveness of digital transformation is another attribute requiring attention, with a relatively low score of 2.23. Building trust in the tangible outcomes of digital transformation is essential to reducing skepticism and promoting adoption.

Additionally, the perceived value of digital transformation in Cluster 0 (2.39) should be strengthened to help schools better understand its long-term benefits and importance in educational development. Finally, while the difference in information evaluation between the two clusters is smaller (2.28 vs. 3.97), improving access to clear and actionable information will still contribute to enhancing understanding and application of digital transformation methods in Cluster 0.

5. Discussion

This research aimed to assess the readiness of school administrators for digital transformation and to identify the primary factors that affect their motivation and capacity to adopt digital technologies in educational leadership. By applying cluster analysis, the study revealed two distinct groups of school leaders exhibiting notably different degrees of readiness, especially regarding their

awareness and confidence in the significance of digital transformation within the education sector. While the general perception among educators and administrators regarding the importance and role of digital transformation is positive, it remains uneven (Ngo, 2021; Tran, 2022).

The first major finding is the clear distinction between two clusters of school administrators, particularly in terms of their commitment, confidence, and perceived value of digital transformation. Cluster 1—representing school leaders with high readiness—demonstrated a strong commitment to implementing digital transformation at their schools. This is reflected in their significantly higher average scores in key dimensions such as commitment to change, belief in the effectiveness of digital transformation, and perceived value of digital transformation. School leaders in this cluster view digital transformation not only as necessary but also as highly beneficial for improving the quality of the educational environment. In contrast, Cluster 0 consists of administrators with lower levels of confidence and commitment to the transformation process. These individuals exhibit limited belief in the effectiveness of digital initiatives and have a reduced perception of the practical value digital transformation can bring to the educational system. These results directly respond to the study's primary research question by showing that readiness is not uniform across educational leadership and is shaped by distinct cognitive and behavioral profiles. This pattern aligns with previous research asserting the central role of leadership capacity in driving digital innovation (Gordashnikova et al., 2021; Koniari & Raftoulis, 2023). Another important finding is the role of awareness and confidence in promoting digital transformation readiness. Administrators in Cluster 1 demonstrated significantly higher confidence in using technology, which positively influenced their readiness to implement digital transformation at their schools. This aligns with the findings of Zeng et al. (2024), who emphasized that confidence in using technology is a strong predictor of success in digital transformation efforts. Moreover, the school leaders in Cluster 1 showed a better understanding of the required resources and time commitment, which is particularly important for ensuring the sustainability of digital initiatives (Makri & Vlachopoulos, 2019).

A second key finding relates to geographical disparities in readiness. Administrators in urban schools—who were more likely to be part of Cluster 1—exhibited higher levels of motivation and strategic engagement in digital transformation compared to their counterparts in rural and remote regions. Although the difference is not particularly large, this finding reflects a broader global trend in which urban schools generally benefit from better infrastructure, more training opportunities, and greater systemic support. In contrast, school leaders in rural areas often face obstacles such as limited technological infrastructure, restricted access to professional development, and inadequate support from higher-level authorities—factors that hinder their ability to lead digital transformation initiatives (Samosa et al., 2023; Dasruth et al., 2024; Garcia et al., 2021; Tanghal & Tanghal, 2022).

The Vietnamese context further amplifies these challenges. The current state of digital transformation in general education reveals incomplete data infrastructure, inconsistent standards, and limited investment in high-quality digital resources. The national education data infrastructure and shared digital resource systems remain incomplete; there is a lack of synchronization and standardization in technical infrastructure and data systems, which hinders connectivity and the formation of a comprehensive digital environment and ecosystem (Trinh, 2023). The scope of digitized data is still limited, with insufficient quality control, resulting in inconsistent knowledge, lack of content verification, and unreliability in terms of accuracy and standards. Moreover, public investment in IT applications and digital transformation in education remains constrained, while efforts to mobilize social resources have yet to prove effective (Nguyen, 2023).

From a policy perspective, the study highlights the necessity of implementing targeted support mechanisms, particularly for school leaders in disadvantaged or low-access areas. In Vietnam, disparities in access to modern technology among urban, rural, and mountainous regions—as well as among different learner groups—pose a risk of educational inequality (Trinh, 2023). Investing in the

development of school leadership capacity through digital leadership training programs and providing adequate resources can help bridge the gap between the two groups. As highlighted by Anderson and Dexter (2005) and Makri and Vlachopoulos (2019), enhancing the digital competencies of school leaders plays a critical role in the successful implementation of digital transformation initiatives in education.

In addition, the results suggest the importance of differentiated professional development. Rather than a one-size-fits-all training approach, school leaders should receive tailored interventions that correspond to their readiness levels and local constraints. This is supported by recent studies that advocate tiered leadership training models based on digital maturity and institutional context (Wijayati et al., 2023; Moradi & Keshmiri, 2021).

Although this study provides valuable insights into the digital transformation readiness of school administrators, it has some limitations. Notably, while the sample size is adequate, the study's geographic scope is restricted to a single region, which may limit the applicability of the results to broader populations. Future research should aim to expand the sampling to encompass multiple and more diverse regions, thereby offering a more comprehensive perspective on the factors affecting readiness across varied educational settings. Additionally, longitudinal studies are encouraged to monitor changes in readiness over time, reflecting administrators' growing experience and ongoing advancements in digital infrastructure.

The results underscore important implications for policy design and implementation in education systems undergoing digital transformation:

Firstly, the readiness gap between clusters—particularly between urban and disadvantaged areas—highlights the necessity of context-aware policy. School leaders in rural or under-resourced regions require tailored support in the form of infrastructure development and leadership capacity-building (Latifah et al., 2022; Samosa et al., 2023).

Furthermore, capacity-building efforts should extend beyond ICT skills to include cultivating digital mindsets, enhancing strategic planning, and fostering motivational leadership. These non-technical factors play a crucial role in overcoming resistance to change and ensuring that digital transformation is deeply embedded in the school culture (Makri & Vlachopoulos, 2019; Okunlola, 2024).

Finally, digital transformation indicators should be institutionalized in national monitoring frameworks. While Vietnam's Ministry of Education and Training has introduced a set of digital benchmarks (MOET, 2022), these should be expanded to include leadership competencies and strategic integration. Without this, efforts may remain surface-level and fail to create lasting organizational change (Hoa, 2022; Oberer & Erkollar, 2018).

In sum, this study not only confirms the multi-dimensional nature of digital readiness among school leaders but also reveals how structural, personal, and institutional factors interact to shape this readiness. These insights offer a valuable basis for designing more responsive and equitable policies to support educational digital transformation.

6. Conclusion

This study investigated school administrators' readiness for digital transformation using cluster analysis, revealing clear differences in commitment, confidence, and perceived value among leader groups. Administrators in favorable environments showed higher readiness, driven by both better access to resources and stronger digital mindsets. These findings enhance understanding of digital transformation in general education and highlight the importance of contextual factors in shaping readiness.

7. Implications

By identifying these distinct readiness profiles, the research enhances understanding of how digital transformation unfolds in the general education context. It also provides a practical foundation for developing targeted capacity-building initiatives that align with the specific readiness levels of school leaders. A cluster-informed approach enables more strategic planning of professional development activities and supports the more effective implementation of digital transformation efforts across diverse educational settings.

8. Limitations

The findings emphasize the need for targeted interventions, especially in areas with limited technological infrastructure and support systems. Prioritizing investment in digital leadership development, ensuring equitable access to digital tools, and establishing mechanisms for continuous support will be essential for narrowing the digital divide and promoting a more inclusive and adaptive education system.

Declarations

Author Contributions. Mai Huong Vu Thi– Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. Bui Quang Vinh: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. Nguyen Thi Minh Nguyet: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. Pham Ngoc Long: Resources, Data curation.

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Declaration of competing interest. The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest in this research

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References

- Abdullah, N. S., & Kadir, S. A. (2023). Relationship between principals' digital leadership and teachers' digital competency in Klang district secondary schools. *Asian Journal of Vocational Education and Humanities*, 4(2), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.53797/ajvah.v4i2.1.2023>
- An, N. X., and Thuy, N.T. (2023). Phát triển thang đo về sự sẵn sàng cho chuyển đổi số của trường trung học phổ thông Việt Nam. *TẠP CHÍ KHOA HỌC GIÁO DỤC VIỆT NAM*. Tập 19, Số S1, Năm 2023. P44-52. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15625/2615-8957/12320108>.
- Anderson, R. E., & Dexter, S. (2005). School technology leadership: An empirical investigation of prevalence and effect. *Educational administration quarterly*, 41(1), 49-82. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013161X04269>
- Asante, K., & Novak, P. (2024). When the push and pull factors in digital educational resources backfire: The role of digital leader in digital educational resources usage. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(6), 6553-6578. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-12095-8>
- Berkovich, I., & Hassan, T. (2022). Principals' digital instructional leadership during the pandemic: Impact on teachers' intrinsic motivation and students' learning. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/17411432221113411>

- Berthold, M. R., Cebron, N., Dill, F., Gabriel, T. R., Kötter, T., Meinl, T., Ohl, P., Thiel, K., & Wiswedel, B. (2009). KNIME—The Konstanz Information Miner: Version 2.0 and beyond. *ACM SIGKDD Explorations Newsletter*, 11(1), 26–31. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1656274.1656280>
- Borg, I., & Groenen, P. J. F. (1997). *Modern multidimensional scaling: Theory and applications*. Springer.
- Carretero, S., Vuorikari, R., & Punie, Y. (2017). DigComp 2.1: The digital competence framework for citizens. Doi: 10.2760/38842 (online)
- Cheng, E. C. K., & Wang, T. (2023). Leading digital transformation and eliminating barriers for teachers to incorporate artificial intelligence in basic education in Hong Kong. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2023.100171>
- Faizan, M., Zuhairi, M. F., Ismail, S., & Sultan, S. (2020). Applications of clustering techniques in data mining: a comparative study. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11(12). DOI: 10.14569/IJACSA.2020.0111218
- Ghomi, M., & Redecker, C. (2019, May). Digital Competence of Educators (DigCompEdu): Development and Evaluation of a Self-assessment Instrument for Teachers' Digital Competence. In *CSEDU (1)* (pp. 541-548). DOI: 10.5220/0007679005410548
- Gordashnikova, O., Fedorchuk, Y., & Kuznetsov, A. (2021). Digital competency of a school principal: the 21st century skill development. In *Edulearn21 Proceedings* (pp. 835-841). IATED. doi: 10.21125/edulearn.2021.0226
- Government of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam (2020), “National Digital Transformation Program to 2025, orientation to 2030”. Decision No. 749/QĐ
- Government of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam (2021). Decision No. 942/QĐ-TTg dated June 15, 2021 of the Prime Minister approving the Strategy for e-Government development towards digital Government for the 2021-2025 period, with a vision to 2030.
- Government of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam (2021). Resolution No. 76/NQ-CP dated July 15, 2021 promulgating the Master Program on State administrative reform for the 2021-2030 period.
- Government of the Socialist Republic of Vietnam (2022). Decision No. 06/QĐ-TTg dated January 6, 2022 of the Prime Minister approving the Project "Developing applications of population data, identification and electronic authentication to serve national digital transformation in the period 2022 - 2025, with a vision to 2030".
- Government of Vietnam. (2021). Decision No. 861/QĐ-TTg dated June 4, 2021, approving the list of communes in ethnic minority and mountainous areas for the 2021–2025 period. Hanoi: Office of the Government.
- Hamzah, N. H., Nasir, M. K. M., & Wahab, J. A. (2021). The Effects of Principals' Digital Leadership on Teachers' Digital Teaching during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Malaysia. *Journal of Education and E-Learning Research*, 8(2), 216-221. DOI: 10.20448/journal.509.2021.82.216.221.
- Hoa, T. T. A. (2022). Khung chính sách chuyển đổi số trong quản lý các cơ sở giáo dục. *TẠP CHÍ KHOA HỌC GIÁO DỤC VIỆT NAM*, Tập 18, Số 12, Năm 2022 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15625/2615-8957/12211201>.
- J. MacQueen (1967). Some methods for classification and analysis of multivariate observations. In: L.M. LeCam, J. Neyman (eds.): Proc. 5th Berkely Symp. Math. Statist. Probab. 1965/66. Univ. of California Press, *Berkely*, vol. 1, 281- 297 (1967)

- Khofi, M. B., & Santoso, S. (2024). Optimize the Role of The State Islamic High School (MAN) Bondowoso Principal in Promoting Digital-Based Learning. *JERIT: Journal of Educational Research and Innovation Technology*, 1(2), 91-102. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.34125/jerit.v1i2.7>
- Kin, T. M., & Kareem, O. A. (2019). School leaders' competencies that make a difference in the era of Education 4.0: A conceptual framework. *International Journal of Academic Research Business and Social Sciences*, 9(5), 214–225. DOI:10.6007/IJARBSS/v9-i4/5836
- Kirinić, V., Hrustek, N. Ž., & Mekovec, R. (2023). "E-Schools Project-Framework for Digital Competencies of School Principals: Competencies in the Area of Digital Technologies in Learning and Teaching," 2023 International Conference on Information Management (ICIM), Oxford, United Kingdom, 2023, pp. 83-87, doi: 10.1109/ICIM58774.2023.00021.
- Koniari, D., & Raftoulis, G. (2023). Digital competence and school leadership in Greece. *Futurity Education*, 3(2). 144-155. <https://doi.org/10.57125/FED.2023.06.25.10>
- König, J., Jäger-Biela, D. J., & Glutsch, N. (2020). Adapting to online teaching during COVID-19 school closure: teacher education and teacher competence effects among early career teachers in Germany. *European journal of teacher education*, 43(4), 608-622. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2020.1809650>
- Kurmanov, N., Bakirbekova, A., & Adilbekuly, M. (2024). The Manager's Digital Competencies in Education System: A Systematic Review. *ECONOMIC Series of the Bulletin of the LN Gumilyov ENU*, (2), 141-157. DOI:10.32523/2789-4320-2024-2-141-157
- Kuzmina-Merlino, I. (2024). Managers' readiness toward digital business transformation: the role of the universities. *Entrepreneurship Education*, 7(2), 173-185. DOI:10.1007/s41959-024-00116-7
- Latifah, R., Budiyanto, C. W., & Saputro, H. (2022). Digital transformation readiness in education: A review. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 12(8), 809-815. Doi: 10.18178/ijiet.2022.12.8.1688
- Luić, L., Švelec-Juričić, D., Lasić-Lazić, J., & Šantalab, M. (2020). Planning, managing and leading the digital transformation of schools. In ICERI2020 Proceedings (pp. 7169-7175). IATED.
- MacQueen, J. (1967). Some methods for classification and analysis of multivariate observations. In L. M. Le Cam & J. Neyman (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Fifth Berkeley Symposium on Mathematical Statistics and Probability* (Vol. 1, pp. 281–297). University of California Press.
- Makri, A., & Vlachopoulos, D. (2019). Professional development for school leaders: A focus on soft and digital skills. *EDULEARN19 Proceedings*, 6200-6209. DOI:10.21125/edulearn.2019.1492
- Marfan, J., & Pascual, J. (2018). Comparative study of school principals' leadership practices: Lessons for Chile from a cross-country analysis. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 46(2), 279-300. DOI:10.1177/1741143217732792
- Masoumi, D., & Noroozi, O. (2023). Developing early career teachers' professional digital competence: A systematic literature review. *European journal of teacher education*, 1-23.
- Ministry of Education and Training (2018). Circular No. 26/2018/TT-BGDĐT of the Ministry of Education and Training: Promulgating regulations on professional standards for preschool teachers.
- Ministry of Education and Training (2021). Decision No. 4998/QĐ-BGDĐT dated December 31, 2021 of the Minister of Education and Training promulgating Technical regulations on data of education and training databases.

- Ministry of Education and Training (2022). Decision No. 4725/QD-BGDDT promulgating the set of indicators to assess the level of digital transformation of general and continuing education institutions.
- Ministry of Education and Training (2023). Directive No. 733/CT-BGDĐT dated May 10, 2023 of the Ministry of Education and Training on rectifying the implementation of regulations related to the abolition of paper household registration books and paper temporary residence books when performing administrative procedures and public services in the field of education.
- Moradi, S., & Keshmiri, S. (2021). Preparing to lead the digital transformation in schools. *School Administration, 9*(2), 358-386. DOI:ORG/10.34785/J010.2021.024
- Nailufar, R., Imaddudin, S., & Muttaqin, R. Z. (2023, May). The Principal's Role In Implementing Digital Literacy In School. In *Proceeding Of International Conference On Education, Society And Humanity* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 524-532).
- Ngô, V.H (2021). https://www.tapchicongsan.org.vn/web/guest/van_hoa_xa_hoi/-/2018/824258/nang-cao-chat-luong-doi-ngu-nha-giao-va-can-bo-quan-ly-giao-duc-trong-giai-doan-hien-nay.aspx
- Nurjani, N., Susanto, N. W., & Hermina, D. (2025). The Concept of Principal's Technology Competency in School Management Effectiveness. *AT-TAKLIM: Jurnal Pendidikan Multidisiplin, 2*(1), 200-214. DOI:10.71282/at-taklim.v2i1.36
- Oberer, B., & Erkollar, A. (2018). Leadership 4.0: Digital leaders in the age of industry 4.0. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership, 7*(4), 404-412. <https://doi.org/10.33844/ijol.2018.60332>
- Okunlola, J. O. (2024). Unpacking the drivers and barriers of digital leadership practice in education: A study of high school leaders' experiences. *Journal of Education and Learning Technology, 207-220*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.38159/jelt.2024573>
- Raftoulis, G. (2021). Educational Leadership and Digital Competence: A Quantitative Study with Directors of Lifelong Learning Institutions in Greece. *Proyecto de investigación*
- Razak, N. A., Rasli, R. M., Subhan, S., Ahmad, N. A., & Malik, S. (2023). Systematic review on digital transformation among teachers in public schools. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education, 12*(2), 1059-1078. DOI:10.11591/ijere.v12i2.24498
- Redecker, C. (2017). European framework for the digital competence of educators: DigCompEdu (No. JRC107466). *Joint Research Centre* (Seville site). DOI: 10.2760/178382 (print)
- Ridho, M. R., & Wiyono, B. B. (2024). Digital leadership of school principals to improve the quality of learning in the industrial revolution era 4.0. DOI:10.24090/insania.v29i1.9566
- Rousseeuw, P. J. (1987). Silhouettes: A graphical aid to the interpretation and validation of cluster analysis. *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics, 20*, 53–65. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-0427\(87\)90125-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0377-0427(87)90125-7)
- Samosa, R., Blanquisco, M. J. P., & De Leon, S. O. N. N. Y. (2023). Towards A Digital School Leadership Framework For Schoolhead And The Teacher Digital Competence: Input For School Leader Digital Learning Guide. *American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750), 1*(5), 102-154. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5119862>
- Stern, M. J., Bilgen, I., & Dillman, D. A. (2014). The state of survey methodology: Challenges, dilemmas, and new frontiers in the era of the tailored design. *Field Methods, 26*(3), 284–301. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1525822X13519561>

- Taber, K. S. (2018). The use of Cronbach's Alpha when developing and reporting research instruments in science education. *Research in Science Education*, 48(6), 1273–1296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2>
- Trần, C.P., et al., (2019). Chuyển đổi số trong giáo dục. Tạp chí Khoa học giáo dục Việt Nam Số 17 tháng 5/2019
- Trịnh, A.H., Trịnh, V.H.,(2023). Thực trạng chuyển đổi số trong quản lý trường mầm non và phổ thông hiện nay. TẠP CHÍ KHOA HỌC GIÁO DỤC VIỆT NAM. Tập 19, Số 12, Năm 2023 2 http://vjes.vnies.edu.vn/sites/default/files/khgdnv_-_tap_19_-_so_12_-_20-27.pdf
- V. Kirinić, N. Ž. Hrustek and R. Mekovec (2023). "E-Schools Project-Framework for Digital Competencies of School Principals: Competencies in the Area of Digital Technologies in Learning and Teaching," 2023 International Conference on Information Management (ICIM), Oxford, United Kingdom, 2023, pp. 83-87, doi: 10.1109/ICIM58774.2023.00021.
- Weiner, B. J. (2009), A theory of organizational readiness for change, *Implement. Sci.*, vol. 4, no.1, pp.1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-4-67>
- Weiner, B. J., Amick, H., & Lee, S. Y. D. (2008). Review: Conceptualization and measurement of organizational readiness for change. A review of the literature in health services research and other fields. *Medical Care Research and Review*, 65(4), 379-436. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1077558708317802>
- Wijayati, P. H., Imron, A., Hadi, S., Nisa, K., & Lestari, A. D. (2023, December). Transformational-Digital Leadership of School Principals for Service Acceleration and Digital Literacy: Empirique Study Literature Review. In 2ND International Conference on Educational Management and Technology (ICEMT 2023) (pp. 146-156). Atlantis Press. DOI:10.2991/978-2-38476-156-2_15
- Zeng, M., Alias, B. S., & Mansor, A. N. (2024). Principals' Digital Leadership and Teachers' Digital Competence: A Systematic. DOI:10.53555/kuey.v30i4.2223

About the Contributor(s)

Nguyen Thi Minh Nguyet is a lecturer in the Department of Educational Management at Hanoi National University of Education (HNUE). She graduated from Hanoi National University of Education with a Bachelor's degree in Philology and Education, a Master's degree, and a Doctoral degree in Education from Hanoi National University of Education. Her primary research interests are educational management and teacher training in educational innovation in Vietnam.

Email: nguyetntm@hnue.edu.vn

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2586-3282>

Vu Thi Mai Huong is a lecturer in the Faculty of Educational Management, Hanoi National University of Education, Vietnam. She holds master's degrees and doctoral degrees of Education from Hanoi National University of Education. Her main research directions are educational management, pre-service and in-service teacher training; teaching methods; autonomy school; education policy; educational curriculum management and learning; and using technologies and ICT in teaching. Relating to her research area, she has written and published books, and several articles in prestigious journals and international conferences.

Email: huongvtm@hnue.edu.vn

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0302-4169>

Bui Quang Vinh is a lecturer at the Department of Software Engineering, Faculty of Information Technology, Hanoi National University of Education (HNUE). His research focuses on the application

of data mining and machine learning techniques to analyze data related to teaching and learning processes. His goal is to uncover hidden patterns in educational systems to provide actionable insights and strategies for improving teaching quality and learning outcomes.

Email: vinhbq@hnue.edu.vn

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5148-6051>

Pham Ngoc Long is a lecturer in the Faculty of Management, National Academy of Education Management, Vietnam. He holds master's degrees and doctoral degrees of Education from Hanoi National University of Education. His research focuses on educational assessment, human resource management and educational management in the context of educational innovation in Vietnam.

Email: longpn@niem.edu.vn

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8979-9888>

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